

**INFLUENCE OF TEACHER RELATED FACTORS
ON STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN KISWAHILI
COMPOSITION IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS
IN KISUMU WEST SUB-COUNTY, KENYA**

Zainab A. Murunga¹ⁱ,

Francis C. Indoshi²,

Tonny O. Okwach³

¹Department of Educational Communication,
Technology and Curriculum Studies,
School of Education, Maseno University,
Kenya

²Senior Lecturer,
Department of Educational Communication,
Technology and Curriculum Studies, Maseno University,
Kenya

³Dr., Department of Curriculum
and Instruction and Educational Media,
Bomet University College,
Kenya

Abstract:

Composition writing helps learners to acquire writing skills. However, students' performance in Kiswahili composition at the Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education (KCSE) examination shows that national performance has been fluctuating with a mean of 14.20 in 2008, 15.40 in 2009, 14.32 in 2010, 16.43 in 2011 and 10.43 in 2012 out of 40 marks. From year 2008 to 2012, Kisumu West Sub-County students' performance in the Joint Evaluation Test (JET) shows that performance was lower compared to other sub-counties in Kisumu County with a mean of 11.20 which was below the county mean of 13.49. Although studies have established that teachers are key determinants of performance, students' academic performance in Kiswahili composition has remained below average in public secondary schools in Kisumu West Sub-County. The purpose of the study was to establish the influence of teacher related factors on students' academic performance in Kiswahili composition in public secondary schools in Kisumu West Sub-County, Kenya. The study employed descriptive survey and correlation designs. Target population was 1622 Form 4 students, 54 teachers of Kiswahili Language, 33 Heads of Department (HOD) and 1 Sub-County Curriculum Support Officer (SCCSO). Purposive sampling technique was used to select a sample of 48

ⁱ Correspondence: email: murungaseti@yahoo.com, findoshi@yahoo.com, tomusonga@gmail.com

teachers, 29 HOD and 1 SCCSO. Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) formula was used to select a sample of 310 Form 4 students. Teacher and student questionnaire, HOD/SCCSO interview schedule and Kiswahili composition test were used for data collection. The study found a positive strong relationship between teacher related factors ($R=.518^*$, $p=.000$) and students' academic performance. It was concluded that an improvement in teacher related factors increased students' academic performance in Kiswahili composition. The study therefore recommends that teachers should be constantly engaged in refresher courses, seminars and symposia to update their skills on Kiswahili language pedagogy so as to improve students' academic performance.

Keywords: teacher related factors, performance and Kiswahili composition

1. Introduction

1.1 Background to the study

The importance of language to humanity is undeniable. Language facilitates expression of thoughts and engagement in the activities that commonly take place in the society (Mosha, 2014). Language can be valuable to its users only when one is able to communicate the desired information in a logical and coherent manner. This is extremely critical in the written form since the author has no opportunity to clarify or explain facts to an inquisitive reader. Therefore, factors that influence students' academic performance in key languages need to be investigated and possible remedies adopted to solve them.

Kiswahili is offered as a subject in various institutions worldwide (Mogere, 2013). Mogere states that by 1977, more than 59 institutions were teaching and conducting research in Kiswahili worldwide. Of these, 24 were in Europe, 18 in the United States of America, Germany had more than 10, two in Asia and five in Africa. He notes that in Britain, the University of London and New York University offer Kiswahili subject to both home and overseas students at both ordinary and advanced levels. Other countries whose universities offer Kiswahili as a foreign language include South Korea, Ghana and Japan. In addition, the language is used in both electronic and print media in British Broadcasting Co-operation (BBC), Deutchewelle, Voice of America, India, Pakistan, Radio Moscow *Idhaa ya Kiswahili* and Beijing China (Mogere, 2013). Moreso, *Urusi Leo* (Russia), *Sauti ya Urafiki* (Germany), *China-Gazeti la Picha* (China) are examples of international print media.

In Africa, the Swahili language is spoken by various communities inhabiting the African Great Lakes Region including Kenya, Tanzania, Uganda, Rwanda, Burundi Mozambique and Democratic Republic of Congo (Mogere, 2013). Mogere asserts that the Kiswahili Language is also offered as a subject in most East African countries. On the same note, in October 2010, 27 Kenyan Kiswahili teachers left for Libya to introduce Kiswahili as a subject (Siringi, 2010). It is important to note that Kenya Broadcasting Co-operation (KBC), Radio Tanzania Dar-es-Salaam (RTD), Radio Rwanda, Voice of

Uganda, Radio South Africa (RSA), and Channel Africa broadcast in either Kiswahili or have Kiswahili programmes.

Although Kiswahili is an important language used for communication in Africa and all over the world today, research on factors that influence academic performance in Kiswahili composition of learners has received minimum focus compared with English and other subject areas. For instance, a study conducted by Khan (2011) to discover the impact of creative writing tests on classroom practice in Pakistan revealed that teachers of English in the area do not teach to develop the creative and communicative abilities of pupils studying the English language. Another study in Saudi Arabia by Endut, Yusoff and Kamarudin (2016) evaluated the level of writing skill among students of Islamic Secondary Schools. It was found out that teacher factor is the most dominant one in determining the level of students' efficiency in writing Arabic.

On the other hand, research such as that of Musau and Migosi (2015) revealed that there was no significant difference in means between teacher qualification and students' academic performance in science, mathematics and technology subjects. Kang'ahi, Indoshi, Okwach and Osodo's (2012) study on the influence of classroom interaction on students' academic achievement in Kiswahili Language indicate that although there exist several factors that influence students' academic achievement, teacher attitude remains one of the major determinants of students' academic achievement. But whether the same attitude of teachers who teach Kiswahili Language also influences students' academic performance in Kiswahili composition is not presented in the study. It is critical to note that studies (Khan, 2011; Endut, et. al., 2016; Musau & Migosi, 2015 and Kang'ahi, et. al., 2012), concentrated on other areas not Kiswahili composition.

According to Kenya National Examination Council report (KNEC, 2012), statistics indicate that despite the importance of Kiswahili language universally, students' academic performance in Kiswahili in Kenya Certificate of Secondary Examination (KCSE) has remained below average compared to English over the years. National Kiswahili composition KCSE performance from the year 2008 to 2012 shows that there was fluctuation in mean scores as follows; 14.20 in 2008, 15.40 in 2009, 14.32 in 2010, 16.43 in 2011 and 10.43 in 2012 out of the possible 40 marks. This dismal performance in Kiswahili could be attributed to poor performance in Kiswahili composition which accounts for 20% of the overall score where the trend seems to be getting lower with the year 2012 recording the lowest mean. Moreover, over the last five years the performance in Kiswahili composition in Joint Evaluation Test (JET) has been on decline in secondary schools in Kisumu County with a mean of 13.49 out of the possible 40 marks. Since Kiswahili subject is compulsory in all secondary schools, students' performance in the subject has been wanting. Further, in Kisumu West Sub-County the students' performance in Kiswahili composition is lower compared to other sub-counties with a mean of 11.20 which is below the county mean as indicated by JET examination report obtained from Sub-County Curriculum Support Office (SCCSO) in Kisumu County. This study used JET results from 2008 to 2012 because KNEC's report

gives Kiswahili composition results at national level with no breakdown at county or sub-county levels. It was noted that all the Sub-Counties within Kisumu County obtained mean scores below the average mean of 20 marks out of the possible 40 marks. Kisumu Central had the highest mean of 14.74, Muhoroni 14.73, Seme 14.20, Nyakach 13.83, Nyando 13.53, Kisumu East 12.16 and Kisumu West Sub-County was the lowest with 11.20 which was below the average county mean of 13.49. This implies that the candidates failed to meet the expected mastery of the subject matter and this resulted to dismal academic performance in Kiswahili composition in KCSE examination.

Several studies have been done to determine influence of teacher related factors on students' academic performance. Rotumoi and Too (2012) observed that teachers' professional status is related to teaching behaviours and interactions they have with children. Asikhia (2010) and Olaleye (2011) argued that teachers' educational qualifications and experience significantly influenced students' academic achievement. When conducting research on factors contributing to under achievement of Zambian female students in O Level Physics examinations, Maguswi (2011) found that lack of qualified teachers of Physics had a significant contribution. In addition, Adaramola and Obomanu (2011) in Nigeria found that lack of qualified teachers led to consistent poor performance of students in Science Mathematics and Technology subjects. In a study, Musau and Migosi (2015) found that there was no significant difference in means between teacher qualification and students' performance in science, mathematics and technology subjects at form four level. This study gives insight to the current study especially in looking at influence of teacher qualification on student's academic performance.

On the contrary, Feng and Sass (2010) found that in-service professional development for teachers has little effect on their ability to increase the achievement gains of students. A study by Aaronson, Barrow and Sander (2007) found little or no difference in teacher effectiveness among Chicago Public School teachers with different college majors. Nonetheless, the influence of professional qualification and teaching experience of teachers on academic performance of students in Kiswahili composition remains unknown.

In addition, teacher attitude and method of teaching can greatly influence students' attitude Yara (2009). Wirth and Perkins (2013) posit that teacher's attitude contributed significantly to student attention in classrooms. Mumasi (2013) opined that teacher attitudes which have been found to be influenced by several factors including the teacher workload caused by inadequate teaching staffs, high rate of teacher absenteeism and transfers influence students' performance. In a research, Rutere (2012) established that implementation of integrated Kiswahili curriculum was going on in public secondary schools and that its success heavily depended on attitudes of teachers of Kiswahili. Similarly, Mokamba, Mokamba, Keraro and Nyagah (2012) study concluded that the negative attitude of Kiswahili teachers towards the reforms and that of students towards learning Kiswahili makes it difficult to implement Kiswahili reforms in the 8.4.4 Kiswahili curriculum. But whether the same attitude in teachers

who teach Kiswahili language also influences student's academic performance in Kiswahili composition is not presented in the studies.

Although, studies have shown that teacher related factors influence students' academic performance, there has been no consensus on the specific teacher factors that influence students' academic performance. However, the important role of the teachers in the learning is unquestionable. Despite the government effort in hiring teachers in secondary schools, there is increased concern over the teacher in-put, hence the introduction of teacher performance contract. This implies that if teachers are not well trained, they will not be able to apply specific abilities hence lack a basic foundation for teaching. Lack of teaching experience will make them more dictatorial in the classroom because they have not mastered the content and acquired classroom management skills to deal with different types of classroom problems. Finally, if the teachers' attitudes and interests are less favorable, then the student is likely to develop negative attitude toward the teacher or Kiswahili composition. As a result, students' performance in Kiswahili composition is likely to be low. In conclusion, it is critical to note that effectiveness of any curriculum depends on the quality of teachers that are there to translate the syllabus into practical instruction materials in the classroom (Moseti, 2007).

1.2 Statement of the problem

The primary aim of writing is to communicate ideas. However, KCSE results indicate dismal performance in Kiswahili composition from year 2008 to 2012. Further, performance of students in Kiswahili composition in Kisumu West Sub-County in JET examination raised concern because students' performance in Kiswahili composition consistently remained lowest compared to other sub- counties in Kisumu County with a mean of 11.20 which is below the county mean of 13.49. While the debate continues worldwide as to what exactly influences students' academic performance, there is little debate as to the influence of teacher related factors on students' academic performance in Kiswahili composition. This relationship has not been empirically measured, yet the academic performance of students in public secondary schools has been relatively low. This study attempted to establish the relationship of the teacher related factors and students' academic performance in Kiswahili composition in public secondary schools in Kisumu West Sub-County, Kenya.

1.3 Purpose of the study

The purpose of this study was to determine the influence of teacher related factors on students' academic performance in Kiswahili composition in public secondary schools in Kisumu West Sub-County, Kenya.

1.4 Objectives of the study

The specific objectives were to:

- 1) Establish the influence of teacher qualification on students' academic performance in Kiswahili composition in public secondary schools in Kisumu West Sub-County, Kenya.

- 2) Ascertain the influence teacher's teaching experience on students' academic performance in Kiswahili composition in public secondary schools in Kisumu West Sub-County, Kenya.
- 3) Determine the influence of teacher's attitude on students' academic performance in Kiswahili composition in public secondary schools in Kisumu West Sub County, Kenya.

2. Literature review

Musau and Migosi (2015) and Ewetan and Ewetan (2015) found that teachers play an important role in determining the students' academic achievement. Despite that, researchers have never reached a consensus on the specific teacher factors that influence students' academic achievement.

Musau and Migosi (2015) found that there was no significant difference in means between teacher qualification and students' performance in science, mathematics and technology subjects at form four. The study applied ex-post-facto survey research design using random sampling to select eight secondary schools in Kitui County. It included eight head teachers, 40 teachers of science, mathematics and technology subjects and 600 candidates who sat for the Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education (KCSE) in the year 2012. Data was collected using questionnaire and document analysis. Analysis used descriptive and inferential statistical tools. This study gave insight to the current study especially in looking at influence of teacher qualification on student's academic performance. However, the researchers applied ex-post-facto survey research design where students' academic performance relied on KCSE 2012 results. The current study employed survey research design where Kiswahili composition test scores were used to measure students' performance.

Similarly, Kosgei, Mise, Odera and Ayugi (2013) sought to establish the relationship between teacher characteristics and students' academic achievement. The study was conducted in Nandi District, Kenya and the target population comprised of teachers of all 26 public secondary schools. The study applied a causal comparative research design. A questionnaire was used for data collection. Data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistical techniques. The study findings suggested that there was no significant relationship between teacher qualification and student academic achievement. In as much as their study applied both descriptive and inferential statistical techniques, data was collected using questionnaires only. In the current study the researcher collected data using questionnaires, interview schedule and Kiswahili composition test to establish the influence of teacher qualification on students' performance in Kiswahili composition.

Kimani, Kara and Njagi (2013) in a study to investigate the teacher factors influencing students' academic achievement in secondary schools in Nyandarua County, concluded that teachers' age, gender, professional qualifications and professional experience did not have significant effect on academic achievement in secondary schools. The study adopted Ex-post facto research design. However, this

study employed mixed methodology comprising descriptive survey and correlation designs to establish the influence of teacher professional qualification on students' academic performance in Kiswahili composition.

In another study, Aaronson, Barrow and Sander (2007) considered teacher quality and student achievement in Chicago public schools. Their study used a gains score approach with controls for student and teacher fixed effects. The results showed strong effects of teachers on student achievement, but traditional measures of teacher qualifications like education, experience, and credential type were noted to have little effect on classroom results. This study was done in a different setting (Chicago public schools), therefore the results could not be generalized to the Kenyan context.

In addition, teachers' attitude plays an important role in the present context. Saidat (2010) mentions that language attitude research has been considered in the previous 50 years because of the growing relation between the importance of the language use and the nature of individuals. Mumasi's (2013) study found that teacher attitudes influence students' performance. The ex-post design was used where the factors which seem to be associated with certain occurrence, conditions or types of behavior were studied. The limitation of this study is that the findings were based on an analysis of what actually happens as the only available means to study causation since it is impracticable to arrange occurrences. Therefore, there was need for further examination to ascertain the influence of teacher attitude on students' academic performance. Rutere's (2012) study investigated the effects of teacher related factors on implementation of integrated Kiswahili curriculum in public secondary schools. The study adopted the descriptive survey design. The study established that implementation of integrated Kiswahili curriculum was going on in public secondary schools and that its success heavily depends on attitudes of teachers of Kiswahili. However, whether teacher attitude influences students' academic performance in Kiswahili composition remains unknown. The current study investigated the influence of teacher related factors on students' academic performance in Kiswahili composition in Kisumu West Sub-County, Kenya.

2. Methodology

2.1 Research design

The study employed mixed methodology comprising descriptive survey and correlation designs. Descriptive survey is used to investigate populations by selecting samples to analyze and discover occurrences. Kumar (2005) argues that the goal of descriptive research is to describe the characteristics of a selected phenomenon and involves the collection of data without manipulation of variables. Correlation was used to show the relationship between the teacher factors and students' academic performance in Kiswahili composition.

2.2 Participants

The study population included 1622 form 4 students, 54 teachers of Kiswahili Language, 33 HOD from 33 secondary schools and 1 SCCSO from Kisumu West Sub-County.

2.3 Sampling technique

To sample students, Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) formula was used 310 respondents were selected. This number was divided by the number of schools (310/33) to yield 9 students per school. Therefore, nine (9) students were selected using systematic sampling method for each school by selecting every ninth student from a randomized class list. Stratified sampling was used to include boys, girls and mixed secondary schools. This was to ensure that each sub-group characteristics is represented in the sample thus raising the external validity of the study. Purposive sampling technique was also used to select 48 teachers of Kiswahili Language, 29 HOD and 1 SCCSO after excluding 10% for pilot study.

2.4 Research instruments

The researcher employed three instruments for the study which included questionnaire for teachers, interview schedule for HOD/SCCSO and Kiswahili composition test for students.

2.5 Data collection procedure

The researcher first developed a proposal under the guidance of supervisors. She sought permission from the Maseno University Ethics and Review Committee, before proceeding to Kisumu West Sub-County office to obtain permission to visit the sampled schools for study. Once permission was granted, the researcher visited each of the sampled schools and sought permission from the Principals and the teachers of Kiswahili Language. Then arrangements were made on the time and date of the study to avoid disrupting lessons. The researcher administered the instruments in person, that is, questionnaires to teachers and interview schedule to HOD. Arrangements were also made with the help of teachers of Kiswahili Language to administer the test to students. Marking was done by the researcher with the help of teachers of Kiswahili Language. Finally, the researcher visited the SCCSO to administer the interview schedule.

2.6 Validity of the research instruments

Face and content validity was used; face validity was determined by consulted experts in the Department of Educational Communication, Technology and Curriculum Studies of Maseno University. Content validity was established through piloting in 10% of the schools under study. The feedback obtained was incorporated in the final instruments before the actual study.

2.7 Reliability of the research instruments

According to Kombo and Tromp (2006) reliability is a measure of how consistent the results from a test are. To achieve this, the study used test retest technique to establish reliability of the instruments prior to the field observation. The procedure involved pilot testing on 4 (10%) of the schools in the Sub-County. A Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 0.816 was obtained.

2.8 Data analysis

Collected data was analyzed by applying descriptive and inferential statistical measure using SPSS. Quantitative data was analysed by use of frequency counts, percentages and means. Inferential statistics: Pearson's product moment correlation (r) was used to analyze the direction of the relationship between teacher related factors and students' performance in Kiswahili composition.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Influence of teacher related factors on students' academic performance in Kiswahili composition

This objective of the study sought to establish the influence of teacher related factors on students' academic performance in Kiswahili composition in public secondary schools. The teacher related factors was defined in terms of professional qualification, teaching experience and attitude. Before the results for the teachers' questionnaire were presented, it was vital to present the results for the students' performance in Kiswahili composition; table 1 shows these results.

Table 1: Students' performance in Kiswahili composition

Grades	Frequency	Percent
A-	2	4.7
B+	1	2.3
B	3	6.9
B-	4	9.3
C+	7	16.3
C	11	25.6
C-	7	16.3
D+	4	9.3
D	2	4.7
D-	2	4.7
Total	43	100.0

From table 1, the study findings revealed that most of the students scored between C+ and C- in Kiswahili composition. This is shown according to 11(25.6%) teachers and 7(16.3%) who said that from marking the composition, students scored C, C+ and C- respectively. Few students scored high grades of A- to B as well as low grades of below C. This showed that, in the schools in Kisumu West Sub-County, the performance of

students in Kiswahili composition was mostly on average. It was indicative from these study findings that the student performance in Kisumu West Sub-County was being affected by some factors which according to the researcher, they were teacher related factors in those schools.

The researcher therefore sought to find out the influence of these teacher factors on the students' performance in Kiswahili composition. To begin with, teachers were asked to indicate their professional qualifications and the results were as displayed in table 2.

Table 2: Teachers' Professional qualification

Professional qualification	Frequency	Percentage
Diploma in Ed.	13	30.2
B.Ed./ PGDE	26	60.5
M.Ed.	4	9.3
PhD in Ed.	0	0.0%

From the results in table 2, it was evident that most of the teachers 26(60.5%) had B.Ed./ PGDE; 13(30.2%) had Diploma in Ed, while 4(9.3%) had M.Ed. Teacher qualification being a requirement for TSC for employing teachers, it was implied from these findings that teacher qualification did not have much influence on student performance. This is because; most of the teachers had the qualifications that were required in order to be employed as a secondary school teacher. To be certain if there was any relationship between teacher qualification and students' academic performance, it was necessary to carry out a correlation test. The findings of correlation were as shown in table 4.6

The researcher also asked the teachers to state their teaching experience in terms of the years they had been in the teaching profession. The study findings were presented as shown in table 3.

Table 3: Teaching experience

Years in teaching	Frequency	Percentage
0-3 years	9	20.9
4-5 years	13	30.2
6-10 years	12	27.9
Above 10 years	9	20.9

The study findings in table 3 revealed that most teachers had a teaching experience of 4-5 years shown by 13(30.2%) teachers. In addition to that, 12(27.9%) teachers had a teaching experience of 6-10 years and 9(20.9%) had a teaching experience of 0-3 years as well as a teaching experience of above 10 years. From these findings, it was discovered that there was an almost even distribution of the teachers' years of teaching experience. This implied that teachers' teaching experience had a moderate relationship with the students' academic performance in Kiswahili composition. However, it was necessary to carry out a correlation analysis for certainty. The correlation analysis results were presented in table 6.

To find out the attitude of teachers in teaching Kiswahili composition, the researcher asked them to fill in a questionnaire using the ratings that were provided as 1- Strongly agree (SA); 2- Agree (A); 3- Uncertain (U); 4- Disagree (D); 5- Strongly disagree (SD). The study findings were presented using frequencies, percentages and means in table 4

Table 4: Teacher attitude

Statement	SA	A	U	D	SD	Mean
Students' best understand when pictures are used in a creative writing lesson.	6 (14.0)	7 (16.3)	7 (16.3)	15 (34.9)	8 (18.6)	3.05
Cartoons improve students' creativity and critical thinking in creative writing.	7 (16.3)	6 (14.0)	3 (7.0)	16 (37.2)	11 (25.6)	3.42
Photographs and mind maps make creative writing lesson interesting.	13 (30.2)	11 (25.6)	4 (9.3)	6 (14.0)	9 (20.9)	2.70
Use of drawings in a creative writing lesson is boring.	8 (18.6)	5 (11.6)	17 (39.5)	6 (14.0)	7 (16.3)	3.00
Charts and magazines enhance students' critical thinking in creative writing lessons.	10 (23.3)	6 (14.0)	4 (9.3)	12 (26.9)	11 (25.6)	3.19
Newspapers do not improve students' understanding in creative writing.	11 (25.6)	14 (32.6)	3 (7.0)	11 (25.6)	4 (9.3)	2.60
Textbooks are boring in teaching creative writing.	12 (26.9)	6 (14.0)	17 (39.5)	3 (7.0)	5 (11.6)	2.19
Models are unnecessary in teaching creative writing.	13 (30.2)	15 (34.9)	6 (14.0)	4 (9.3)	5 (11.6)	2.28
Oral narratives improve students' imagination in creative writing lessons.	16 (37.2)	12 (26.9)	3 (7.0)	6 (14.0)	6 (14.0)	2.40
Novels/class readers are a waste of time when teaching creative writing.	5 (11.6)	10 (23.3)	6 (14.0)	9 (20.9)	13 (30.2)	3.35
Students' best understand when poems are used in creative writing lessons.	8 (18.6)	5 (11.6)	6 (14.0)	13 (30.2)	11 (25.6)	3.23
Plays do not enhance students' critical thinking in creative writing.	8 (18.6)	11 (25.6)	5 (11.6)	8 (18.6)	11 (25.6)	3.07
Debates make teaching of creative writing enjoyable.	11 (25.6)	17 (39.5)	- (-)	8 (18.6)	7 (16.3)	2.63
Radio lessons make creative writing lessons interesting.	12 (26.9)	15 (34.9)	8 (18.6)	5 (11.6)	3 (7.0)	2.26
Television is useless in teaching creative writing.	17 (39.5)	16 (37.2)	2 (4.7)	5 (11.6)	6 (14.0)	2.35
Computers enhance students' creativity in creative writing lessons.	7 (16.3)	7 (16.3)	5 (11.6)	13 (30.2)	11 (25.6)	3.40
Use of field trips to teach creative writing is a waste of time.	11 (25.6)	8 (18.6)	5 (11.6)	7 (16.3)	12 (26.9)	3.02
Overall mean						2.83

The study findings in table 4 showed the responses of teachers concerning their attitude towards teaching creative skills. It was evident from the study findings that most teachers, 15(34.9%) disagreed with 8(18.6%) strongly disagreeing with the fact that students best understand when pictures are used in creative writing lessons. However,

some 7(16.3%) agreed and another group similar to that was uncertain while 6(14.0%) strongly agreed. From a mean of 3.05, it showed that there were mixed up opinions from teachers hence they were uncertain about their attitude in teaching writing skills. It was also clear from the table that most teachers were uncertain concerning the use of cartoons, drawing, charts and magazines in teaching creative writing; (M=3.42, 3.00 and 3.19) respectively. On the contrary, teachers agreed and strongly agreed that photographs and mind maps make creative writing lessons interesting, (M=2.70). In addition to that, teachers agreed and strongly agreed that newspapers do not improve students' understanding, use of text books is boring and that models are unnecessary in teaching creative writing, (M=2.60, M=2.19, M=2.28) respectively. Furthermore, most teachers agreed that oral narratives improve students' imagination in creative writing lessons, (M=2.40).

Table 4 also revealed that teachers were uncertain whether novels/class readers, poems and plays enhanced creative writing lessons or not. This was suggested by means of 3.35, 3.23 and 3.07 respectively.

There was an agreement for most teachers, (M=2.63), that debates make teaching of creative writing enjoyable. The same trend was also seen where most teachers agreed, (M=2.26) that radio lessons make creative writing interesting, and that use of television in teaching creative writing is useless (M=2.35). Uncertainty was seen in the teachers' responses concerning use of computers and field trips in teaching creativity writing, (M=3.40, M=3.02) respectively.

Table 5: Means for teacher related factors on performance in Kiswahili composition

Factors	Respondents	N	Mean
Professional Qualification	Teachers	43	1.79
Teacher Attitude	Teachers	43	2.83
Teaching Experience	Teachers	43	3.72

Key: Interpretation of Mean Ratings for teacher attitude

1.00 – 1.44: Strongly Agree

1.45 – 2.44: Agree

2.45 – 3.44: Uncertain

3.45 – 4.44: Disagree

4.45 – 5.00: Strongly Disagree

Key: Interpretation of Mean Ratings for teacher qualification and teaching experience

1.00 – 1.44: Low

1.45 – 2.44: Moderate

2.45 – 3.44: High

3.45 – 4.44: Very high

From Table 5, it can be noted that the sampled respondents agreed that professional qualification had a moderate influence on performance in Kiswahili composition as the teachers' rating was (M=1.79).

Interview findings concurred with this finding, as interviewees emphasized that professional qualification of a teacher influences academic performance of learners to some extent. This was highlighted in a statement by one interviewee that:

“Ability of a teacher to offer sufficient instructions to learners lay in professionalism of the teacher. This determines the teacher’s mastery of the subject matter, enables a teacher to prepare adequately and to monitor learning progress in students in proper manner. Therefore in most cases teachers with higher academic qualifications produce better student achievement in Kiswahili composition compared with those who have less academic qualifications. However, this is not the case in all cases; teachers with diploma can be seen to produce better results than those with degree or even masters.” (HoD4)

Study findings suggesting that professional qualification of a teacher has moderate influence on students’ performance in Kiswahili composition concurs with findings by Huang and Moon (2009) who documents that teacher qualification accounted for approximately 40 to 60 percent of the variance in average of students’ achievement in assessment. Interaction within the classroom between the teacher and the student as managed by professionally qualified teacher can result into improved academic performance of students, as noted by Mosesti (2007). However, findings in Musau and Migosi (2015), which assessed the extent to which teacher qualification influences students’ academic performance in science, Mathematics and Technology subjects tend to contradict these findings. They (Musau & Migosi, 2015) found that there was no significant difference in means between teacher qualification and students’ performance in science, mathematics and technology subjects at form four level. It can therefore be concluded that as much as professional qualification may not influence performance of students in sciences, the same has significant influence in performance in Kiswahili composition.

Equally, Table 5 illustrates that teaching experience had a very high influence on performance in Kiswahili composition as the teachers’ rating was (M=3.72). This finding implies that the more teaching experience a teacher has, the better performance in Kiswahili composition would be realized.

Similar findings were revealed during interviews with HoDs and the SCCSO. The interviewees stated that experience held by teachers is a vital tool for enhancing lesson delivery and assessment of learning progress. This was captured in a statement by one HoD who stated that:

“Teacher gains skills through experience and the more experience a teacher has, the more successful he/she will be in his or her work. Experienced teachers give the schools stability and serve as mentors to the new teachers. Teaching experience enables a teacher to adequately handle successfully both slow and fast learners in one classroom. In addition, more experienced teachers are considered to be more able to concentrate on the most appropriate way to teach particular topics to students who differ in their abilities, prior knowledge and backgrounds. Given that learning takes place inside classroom, setting up of suitable environment is an essential step in ensuring better performance. Experience in teaching therefore enables setting up of such environments.” (HoD10)

Understanding the needs of individual learners forms a strong base for designing methods of instruction for any teacher. Experienced teachers understand the needs of different learners. This findings support what Rutere (2012) established, that there exists a link between implementation of integrated Kiswahili curriculum and the teaching experiences. For this matter, teacher experience enables implementation of Kiswahili composition curriculum. Moreover, Ewetan and Ewetan (2015) also found that teaching experience has significant influence on students' academic performance in Mathematics and English Language in Nigeria. The findings, however, seem to contradict what Aaronson, et al (2007) found that traditional measures of teacher qualifications like experience, among others, have little effect on classroom results in study done in Chicago (USA). But for Kiswahili composition specifically, teacher experience seems to be a vital quality for the enhancement of students' performance.

Table 5 also indicates uncertainties concerning the teacher attitude influence on students' performance in Kiswahili composition, as the teachers' rating was (M=2.83). Interview findings however tended to contrast this finding by elaborating the fact that attitude of teachers towards a subject extend to the learners who will in turn hold similar attitude. Poor attitude of some teachers towards Kiswahili as a subject tends to spillover to students who then exhibit the same in poor performance in composition writing. This was highlighted in a statement by one interviewee that:

“Teacher’s attitude directly affect students’ attitude. What teachers do is a reflection of what they know and believe, and that teacher knowledge and ‘teacher thinking’ provide the underlying framework which guides the teacher classroom actions. Some Kiswahili teachers display poor attitude towards Kiswahili subject, reasoning that the language is not used for official written communication in Kenya. Others use English language to give illustration or communicate with students in the classroom during Kiswahili lessons. These in turn make the students to develop a negative attitude toward the subject. (HoD7)

This implies that some teachers lay emphasis on languages that are used for official written communication. Apparently, most correspondences in contemporary offices in Kenya use English language as opposed to Kiswahili, hence the limited emphasis. In another interview, the researcher captured the following statement:

“Kiswahili is a compulsory subject in both primary and secondary schools in Kenya. Therefore, the fact that there are few trained Kiswahili teachers means that teacher workload is high. This in turn results into poor attitude of teachers towards Kiswahili, further leading to poor performance in the subject.” (SCCSO)

Poor attitude towards Kiswahili and the resulting poor performance in Kiswahili composition thus lead to few people enrolling for the subject in teacher colleges and universities: the snowball effect of attitude is therefore spreading large. Poor attitude of teachers towards Kiswahili composition has also been confirmed by Mokamba, et al

(2012) in an investigation on factors affecting implementation of Kiswahili curriculum. They concluded that the negative attitude of Kiswahili teachers towards the reforms and that of students towards learning Kiswahili makes it difficult to implement Kiswahili reforms in the 8.4.4 Kiswahili curriculum. In addition, Mumasi (2013) also found that teacher attitudes which have been found to be influenced by several factors including the teacher workload caused by inadequate teaching staffs, high rate of teacher absenteeism and transfers influence students' performance in Kiswahili.

Table 6: Correlation between teacher factors and students performance in Kiswahili composition

		Mean teacher factors	Mean student performance
Mean teacher factors	Pearson Correlation	1	.518**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	43	43
Mean student performance	Pearson Correlation	.518**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	43	43
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			

Table 6 showed that there was a strong, positive and significant relationship between overall teacher related factors and the performance in students' Kiswahili composition ($R=.518$, $p=.000$). This implied that if the teacher factors were favorable, then the students would perform well in Kiswahili composition writing, and if they were not favorable, then students' performance in Kiswahili composition would be dismal. Therefore, teacher related factors, in this case, teacher qualification, teaching experience and attitude.

4. Conclusions

An improvement in teacher related factors increased students' academic performance in Kiswahili composition.

5. Recommendations

The study recommends that teachers should be constantly engaged in refresher courses, seminars and symposia to update their skills on Kiswahili language pedagogy so as to improve students' academic performance.

References

Aaronson, D., Barrow, L. & Sander, W. (2007). Teachers and Student Achievement in the Chicago Public High Schools. *Journal of Labor Economics*, 25(1), 95-135.

- Asikhia O. A. (2010). Students and teachers' perception of the causes of poor, academic performance in Ogun State secondary schools [Nigeria]: Implications for counseling for national development, *European Journal of Social Sciences*, 13(2), 229-242.
- Endut, S., Yusoff, N. M. R. N. & Kamarudin, M. Y. (2016). Factors That Influence Efficiency of Writing Essays in Arabic e. *Creative Education*, 7, 435-442.
- Feng L., Sass T. R. (2010). What Makes Special Education Teachers Special? Teacher Training and Achievement of Students with Disabilities. CALDER Working Paper No. 49. Washington, D.C.: The Urban Institute.
- Kang'ahi, M., Indoshi, F. C., Okwach, T. O. & Osodo, J. (2012). Teaching Styles and Learners' Achievement in Kiswahili Language in Secondary Schools. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development* 1 (3) 62 – 87.
- KNEC (2012). *K.C.S.E newsletter*. Nairobi: KNEC.
- Kimani, G. N., Kara, A. M. & Njagi, L. W. (2013). Teacher factors influencing students' academic Achievement. *International Journal of Education and Research* Vol. 1 No. 3.
- Kosgei, A., Mise, J. K., Odera, O. & Ayugi, M. E. (2013). Influence of teacher characteristics on students' academic achievement among secondary schools. *Journal of Education and Practice* 4, (3), 76 – 82.
- Krejcie, R. V. & Morgan, D. W. (1970). Determining Sample Size for Research Activities, *Journal of Educational and Psychological Measurement*, Vol. 30, No 30, pp. 607-610. State: Publisher.
- Mogere, G. N. (2013). *Teachers' instructional strategies in insha and their influence on class seven pupils' performance in Garissa County-Kenya*. Unpublished thesis submitted to the Kenyatta University.
- Mokamba, R. M., Mokamba, J., Keraro, V. & Nyagah, G. (2012). Factors affecting implementation of Kiswahili curriculum reforms. *Prime Journal of Business Administration and Management (BAM)*. ISSN: 2251-1261. Vol. 2(11).
- Moseti, P. (2007). *Teaching/Learning strategies in integrated English course and their effects on performance in Manga Division, Nyamira District*. Unpublished M.Ed Thesis Kenyatta University.
- Mosha, M. A. (2014). Factors Affecting Students' Performance in English Language in Zanzibar Rural and Urban Secondary Schools. *Journal of Education and Practice* 5, (35), 64 – 77.
- Musau, L. M, Migosi, J. & Muola, J. M. (2013). Determinants of girls' performance in science, mathematics and technology subjects in public secondary schools in Kenya. *Int. J. Educ. Adm. Policy Studies*. 5(3):33-42.
- Musau, L. & Migosi, J. A. (2015). Teacher qualification and students' academic performance in science mathematics and technology subjects in Kenya. *International Journal of Educational Administration and Policy Studies* Vol. 7(3), pp. 83-89.

- Mumasi, W. (2013). *School based factors influencing students' performance at Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education in Narok North District, Kenya*. Unpublished master thesis, University of Nairobi, Kenya.
- Olaleye, F. O. (2011) Teachers Characteristics As Predictor Of Academic Performance Of Students In Secondary Schools In Osun State –Nigeria *European Journal of Educational Studies* 3(3),pp 505-511
- Rutere, J. K. (2012). *Effects of teacher related factors on implementation of integrated Kiswahili curriculum in public secondary schools*. Unpublished master's thesis, University of Nairobi, Kenya.
- Saidat, A, M. (2010). Language Attitude: The Case of Jordan. *International Journal of Academic Research*, 2, 235–243.
- Siringi, S. A. (2010, October 13). Libya hires Kenyan Kiswahili graduates. *Daily Nation* p.11.
- Yara, P. O. (2009). Students' attitude towards mathematics and academic achievement in some selected secondary schools in south-western Nigeria. *Eur. J. Sci. Res.*, 36(3): 336-341.

Creative Commons licensing terms

Author(s) will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Education Studies shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflicts of interest, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated into the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).